

of b.p. 60–80°. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

Reaction of epoxide 1 with urea: 3 α ,4 α -Epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)^a (1.5 g, 3.77 mmol) in *N,N*-dimethyl formamide (25 ml) was refluxed with urea (1.5 g) for about 6 h. It was then poured in ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvents provided an oil (1.35 g) which was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (30.0 g). Elution with petroleum ether–ether (8:1) gave 6-nitrocholest-5-eno[4 α ,3 α -*d*]oxazolidin-2'-one (2) which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (0.4 g, 26.67%), m.p. 120° (Found: C, 71.09; H, 9.32; N, 5.88. C₂₉H₄₄N₂O₄ requires: C, 71.18; H, 9.32; N, 5.92%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 490 (NH), 1 715 (oxazolidinone moiety)⁴, 1 640 (C=C), 1 535 and 1 375 cm⁻¹ (C–NO₂); δ (CDCl₃) 7.94 (1H, brs, NH exchangeable with deuterium), 5.15 (1H, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 7 Hz, C₂ β –H, equatorial), 4.27 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, C₄ β –H, pseudo-axial)⁵, 1.21, 0.93, 0.83 and 0.68 (angular and sidechain methyl protons); and elution with petroleum ether–ether (4:1) furnished 6-nitrocholest-5-eno-[3 α ,4 α -*d*]oxazolidin-2'-one (3) which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (0.3 g, 20%), m.p. and m.m.p.^a 137° (Found: C, 71.30; H, 9.25; N, 5.80. C₂₉H₄₄N₂O₄ requires: C, 71.18; H, 9.32; N, 5.93%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 420 (NH), 1 725 (oxazolidinone moiety)⁴, 1 650 (C=C), 1 525 and 1 365 cm⁻¹ (C–NO₂); δ (CDCl₃) 8.01 (1H, brs, NH exchangeable with deuterium), 5.48 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, C₄ β –H, pseudo-axial)⁵, 3.98 (1H, mc, $W_{1/2}$ 7 Hz, C₂ β –H, equatorial), 1.20, 0.88, 0.78 and 0.66 (angular and side chain methyl protons).

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. M. S. Ahmad and Prof. S. M. Osman, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities and to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial support.

References

- 1 R. B. FUGITT and R. W. LUCKENBAUGH, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, 97, 109990; W. ECKHARDT, W. KUNZ and A. HUBBLE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1981, 95, 150642; T. TAKEMATSU, T. HISADA, T. MOTEGI, H. TSUCHIYA and M. FURUSHIMA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 83, 2319; H. IGARASHI, T. KURIHARA and H. TAKEDA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 99445; G. HUGONET, C. FAURAN, C. DOUZON, R. COLLETTE and G. GOURRET, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, 82, 112058.
- 2 SHAMUULLAH, S. HUSAIN and M. R. ANSARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 662.
- 3 SHAMUULLAH, S. HUSAIN, D. M. BASHA and I. H. SIDDIQUI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 849.
- 4 I. J. BELLAMY, "Advances in Infrared Group Frequencies", Chapman and Hall, London, 1968, p. 165.
- 5 N. S. BHACCA and D. H. WILLIAMS, "Application of NMR Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", Holden Day, San Francisco, 1964, pp. 47–49, 73.

Synthesis of *n*-Alkyl Substituted-pyrazoles using Vilsmeier–Haack Reaction†

R. A. PAWAR* and A. P. BORSE

S. S. V. P. S' Late Karmveer Dr. P. R. Ghogarey Science College, Dhule-424 002

Manuscript received 20 June 1988, accepted 12 October 1988

THERE is considerable interest in Vilsmeier–Haack reaction and its synthetic applications¹. In continuation of our interest in Vilsmeier–Haack reaction², we report here syntheses of 4-*n*-alkylsubstituted pyrazoles (Scheme 1) from phenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and azines of 2-*n*-acyl-5-chlorophenols by monoformylation and cyclisation using one mole of the Vilsmeier–Haack reagent (DMF/POCl₃). A general mechanistic scheme for this reaction is also suggested.

Synthesis and spectroscopic properties of 2-*n*-acyl-5-chlorophenols (1a–d) and their phenylhydrazones (2a–d) have been described by us earlier³. The phenylhydrazones (2a–d) and one mole of the reagent (DMF/POCl₃) were stirred for 6 h and the reaction mixture was then neutralised with NaOH giving 1-phenyl-3-(2'-hydroxy-4'-chlorophenyl)-4-*n*-alkylpyrazoles (3a–d) (Table 1). Structures of the compounds were established by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data. Ir spectra of 3a–d showed characteristic bands for pyrazole ring⁴ at 1 597, 1 553, 1 480 and 1 310 cm⁻¹ and nmr spectra, e.g. of 3d (60 MHz, CCl₄, TMS) showed chemical shifts at δ 1.00 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.5 (4H, m, (CH₂)₂), 2.7 (2H, t, CH₂), 10.8 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable strongly H-bonded OH) and 7.8 (9H, m, ArH).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. taken no.	Pyrazole formed		Yield %	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
	No.	M.p. °C		
2a	3a	138	30	9.47 (9.82)
2b	3b	98	26	9.13 (9.36)
2c	3c	109	20	8.62 (8.95)
2d	3d	107	20	8.21 (8.57)

Plausible mechanism for the above cyclisation is presented in Chart 1. Phenylhydrazone in tautomeric form (II) acts as a nucleophile towards a reactive intermediate obtained from DMF/POCl₃ to give III. Addition of OPOCl₂ to carbon–carbon double bond of III affords IV. This step is facilitated due to ease in formation of five-membered ring. Activated complex IV is then converted by base-induced elimination reaction to pyrazole V.

† Presented at the National Symposium on Recent Advances in Organic Chemistry, University of Poona.

NOTES

2. R. A. PAWAR and S. M. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 304; R. A. PAWAR, A. L. KOHAK and V. N. GOGTE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, 14, 375; R. A. PAWAR, 9th IOHO, Japan, 1983, Abstracts G-144, 506.
3. R. A. PAWAR, R. D. SHINGTE and V. N. GOGTE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 522; R. A. PAWAR and V. N. GOGTE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 921.
4. A. R. KATRITZKY and A. P. AMBLER, in "Physical Methods in Heterocyclic Chemistry", ed. A. R. KATRITZKY, Academic, New York, 1968, Vol. II, p. 232.
5. E. S. GOULD, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Rinehart of Winston, New York, 1959, p. 150.

appearing at δ 6.2–9.1 were supported by D_2O exchange. In case of the amides (1, 2; R' =n-alkyl) signal due to $CH=CR$ proton was observed at δ 8.2–8.4.

1

- 1a; $R=2-NO_2$, $R'=H$, n-alkyl (C_1-C_6)
 1b; $R=3-NO_2$, $R'=H$, n-alkyl (C_1-C_6)
 1c; $R=4-NO_2$, $R'=H$, n-alkyl (C_1-C_6)
 1d; $R=2-Cl$, $R'=H$, OH_2 , C_2H_5
 1e; $R=3-Cl$, $R'=H$, OH_2 , C_2H_5
 1f; $R=4-Cl$, $R'=H$, OH_2 , C_2H_5

Synthesis and J.H. Activity of *N*-(Substituted)-yl-3-(sub-1'-phenyl)acrylamides and *N*-(Substituted)-yl-2-alkyl-3(sub-1'-phenyl)-acrylamides

M. S. BHATIA*, ARVINDER KAUR, B. KAUR
and

XAVIER M. CHERIAN**

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University,
Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 11 April 1988, revised 18 September 1988,
accepted 12 October 1988

2

- 2a; $R=2-NO_2$, $R'=H$, CH_3 , C_2H_5
 2b; $R=3-NO_2$, $R'=H$, CH_3 , C_2H_5 , n- C_6H_{11}
 2c; $R=4-NO_2$, $R'=H$, OH_2
 2d; $R=2-Cl$, $R'=H$, OH_2
 2e; $R=3-Cl$, $R'=H$, OH_2
 2f; $R=4-Cl$, $R'=H$, OH_2

J.H. activity: The compounds (1 and 2) were screened* for their J.H. activity against Indian red cotton bug.

Among amides of cinnamic acid and (*o*, *m*, *p*)-nitro-substituted acids with cyclohexylamine, *p*-nitro-substituted compound (1c; $R'=H$) showed the highest activity. Activity decreased as nitro group moved from *para* to *ortho* position. Similar trend in activity was observed in case of chloro-substituted amides (*para* > *meta* > *ortho*). As the length of the alkyl chain at C-2 of 1c was increased, a decrease in activity was noted. Replacement of cyclohexyl system in 1 by pyrazolone system 2 showed increase in activity.

Experimental

M.p./b.p. were uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on a EM/390 (90 MHz) spectrometer. Hplc was carried out on a Simadzu-LCUA instrument. All the compounds showed satisfactory elemental analysis and spectral data.

General procedure for preparation of substituted acrylic acids: To sodium hydride (0.1 mol, 50% emulsion in mineral oil) was taken in dry THF (75 dm³), appropriate Wittig's salt (0.1 mol) was added dropwise with stirring keeping temperature below 20° and the reaction mixture was further stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The contents were then cooled and decomposed with excess water. The organic material was extracted with ether and the

DURING the past two decades, efforts are being made to find an alternative mode of insect control because of their poisonous nature to non-target organisms and resistance by insects. Causing disarrangement of insect growth processes with their own hormones or related compounds, specifically with J.H. analogues, has been the subject of interest¹.

In continuation to our earlier studies² on the synthesis and J.H. activity of multifunctional amides, a number of substituted amides (1 and 2) have been synthesised and tested for their J.H. activity on Indian red cotton bug.

Substituted cinnamic acids were prepared through the applications of modified Wittig's reaction³ with appropriate reagents on *o*-, *m*- and *p*-substituted-benzaldehydes followed by hydrolysis with aqueous base.

Reaction of substituted cinnamic acids with an amine in presence of $POCl_3$ /triethylamine in dichloromethane furnished the required amides (1 and 2), whose structures were confirmed by pmr and hplc.

Double bond fixed by modified Wittig's reaction was predominantly *E* confirmed by hplc analysis which exhibited two peaks with average retention time of 2.6 (97.2%) and 3.2 (2.8%) corresponding to *E* and *Z* isomers, respectively. It is also attributed to the presence of pmr signals at δ 8.6 and 6.25 ($-CH=CH-$). The presence of NH protons

**Present address: Department of Chemistry, The Ohio State University, U.S.A.